

GENERATION OF A DIGITAL ELEVATION MODEL USING CAPELLA HIGH-RESOLUTION SAR DATA: FIRST RESULTS OVER LA PALMA ISLAND

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ABSTRACT

Generation of Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) using Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data is a valid flexible alternative to other surveying techniques. In this work we adopt radargrammetry on two SAR images recorded by the Capella Space X-band spaceborne sensor on two consecutive days over La Palma Island (Canary Islands, Spain) during the Cumbre Vieja volcanic eruption, with the aim of investigating the potential of these high-resolution (up to 0.7 by 0.5 m²) SAR images in generating precise DEMs. The adopted method employs a multilook-based spatial filter followed by an iterative region-growing algorithm to identify matching pixels between the two images. The resultant radargrammetric DEM is compared with a Lidar-based DEM, showing a good agreement in the areas less affected by lava flow.

Index Terms— digital elevation model, radargrammetry, high-resolution SAR imagery, volcano monitoring.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) are a widely used tool to study the Earth's surface for several applications, such as earthquake and volcano monitoring, urban planning, mining activity surveying, and biomass analysis. Radar images, collected by spaceborne Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) sensors, have demonstrated a good potential in generating DEMs. Furthermore, the all-weather cloud-penetrating capability of spaceborne SAR technology is increasingly relevant for DEM applications [1]. The extraction of three-dimensional maps can be realized using SAR data by means of few different techniques, such as interferometry and radargrammetry [2][3][4]. Interferometry exploits the phase difference between two SAR images collected with a wide spatial baseline, whereas radargrammetry employs the disparity between two SAR amplitude images [5]. Generally, interferometric techniques have shown a higher accuracy, but suffer from the loss of interferometric

coherence due to temporal decorrelation of the radar scatterers. On the other hand, amplitude-based radargrammetry is more robust against atmospheric disturbance but is affected by the granular interference typical in SAR amplitude images, called speckle [1]. This spatial disturbance often decreases the correlation between two SAR amplitude images of the same area and is mitigated using spatial filtering techniques, which in turn decrease the image spatial resolution. Consequently, the point cloud that generates the radargrammetric DEM is less dense.

However, the recent availability of high-resolution SAR images, collected by the recently launched Capella Space SAR mission, makes viable the generation of accurate radargrammetric DEMs. Capella satellites mount an X-band radar sensor, which can work in Spotlight, Sliding Spotlight or Stripmap modes, achieving a spatial resolution of 0.7 by 0.5 m² in Spotlight mode [6].

The case study analysed in this work is located in the southwest part of La Palma Island (Canary Islands, Spain). This area was affected by the Cumbre Vieja volcanic eruption, which started on 19th September 2021 and ended on 13th December 2021, with a maximum volcanic explosivity index (VEI) of 3. The eruption caused the evacuation of about 7000 people, due to the ejection of volcanic gases and pyroclastic material as well as lava flow, which covers an area of more than 1200 hectares reaching the ocean to form two lava deltas. The length of the lava flows is greater than 6.5 km (subaerial) and 1.1 km (submarine) [7].

The radargrammetry-based DEM generation implemented in this work makes use of an iterative region-growing algorithm to select matching pixels between two SLC SAR amplitude images. The elevation value for each point is estimated using the radargrammetry principle, thus forming a point cloud, which is then geocoded and spatially interpolated to generate the final DEM. It should be noted that the input amplitude images are first spatially filtered using a small multilook window in order to mitigate speckle. However, due to the high spatial resolution of the input data,

the spatial filtering does not compromise the accuracy of the estimated radargrammetric DEM.

The main contribution of this work is an investigation of the potential of high-resolution SAR images in generating DEM using the radargrammetry technique, as a viable alternative to other surveying techniques and interferometric SAR techniques. A preliminary performance evaluation is realized by comparing the radargrammetric DEM with a publicly available high-precision DEM generated using a lidar sensor in the areas of the analysed scene not affected by lava flow. Furthermore, the final version of the paper is expected to provide a first qualitative analysis of the lava volume covering some portions of the area under study.

This paper is organized as follows: section 2 illustrates the methodology utilized for radargrammetric DEM generation, section 3 describes the system and dataset, section 4 illustrates the obtained results, final remarks are drawn in section 5.

2. METHODOLOGY

In order to generate the DEM from a pair of SLC intensity images, we adopted a traditional radargrammetric approach, which can be summarized by the following steps:

1) *Co-registration and resampling*, i.e. registration of the slave image with respect to the master image, which consists of a rotation and resampling of the slave image, yielding two overlapping images;

2) *Speckle Filtering*, which is performed by a multilook operation, with the cost of decreasing the spatial resolution;

3) *Matching* between co-registered images, which aims at identifying a set of points with high coherence across the two images. This operation is realized using a *region-growing* algorithm, which recursively forms a set of high-coherence point pairs, using as input a set of points that have been selected manually after a visual examination. In the first step, a number of 10-20 points associated with high-energy stable scatterers are identified as *seed points*, then the region-growing algorithm works as follows:

a) candidate points are identified among the higher-energy points within a maximum distance (d_{max}) from each seed point in the master and slave image;

b) the spatial cross-correlation between each pair of candidate points is computed, using a L-by-L;

c) the pairs of candidate points with a cross-correlation higher than a predefined threshold, λ , are selected and added to the point set.

This sequence of steps yields a new set of seed points, for a further region-growing iteration. The region growing operation is repeated iteratively until the increase in the number of selected points is negligible.

4) *DEM generation*. The imaging geometry is used to calculate the elevation for each couple of points identified by the automatic matching stage [2-3]. In particular, for each couple of matching points the range, Doppler and ellipsoid equations are applied, where the only unknown is represented by the elevation. The aim consists of find the

value of the elevation that minimizes the distance between the two rays, associated to the line-of-sight of the master and slave images. The minimum point search is performed by a golden section search, where the search interval is previously set between 0 and 2000 m. Then, each point is geocoded to obtain a point cloud with associated elevation value. Finally, the elevation pattern point cloud is spatially interpolated to obtain the final radargrammetric DEM.

3. DATASET DESCRIPTION

The area under analysis is located in the south-west part of La Palma Island in the Canary Island archipelago. The map in Figure 1 shows the case area, together with a layer indicating the geographical extension of the lava flow due to the Cumbre Vieja volcanic eruption. The terrain elevation ranges roughly from 0 to 2000 m, with a mix of bare soil, small urban conglomerations, cultivated and forested land, whereas the lava flow has an average height of 12 m, reaching a maximum of 70 m [7]. The two analysed SLC SAR images were collected by Capella Space SAR sensor La Palma Island on October 2 (image 1) and 3 (image 2), 2021. The main radar and acquisition parameters are summarized in Table 1.

Feature	Value
Sensor	Capella Space-3 SAR
Trajectory	Descending
Beam Mode	Spotlight
Polarization	HH
Carrier Frequency	9.65 GHz (X-band)
Antenna Orientation	Same-side-looking (left)
Pixel Spacing (range x azimuth)	0.7 m x 0.5 m
Master/Slave Image Date	October 2/3,2021
Master/Slave Image Incidence Angle	$\sim 33^\circ/\sim 29^\circ$
Squint Angle	~ 0
Orbit Azimuth Direction	-191°

Table 1- Main radar and acquisition parameters

Figure 1 – Area under analysis, with a layer indicating the areas covered by lava flows, provided by the Copernicus EMS Rapid Mapping service (<https://emergency.copernicus.eu/EMSR546>). Colour scale indicates the dates of the lava flows (from 20 September to 17 December 2021).

(a)

(b)

Figure 2 –Multilooked SLC SAR amplitude images recorded by the Capella Space on-board sensor over La Palma Island on 2 (a) and 3 (b) October, 2021. Multilook window of 3 by 3, spatial resolution: 1.2 m (range) by 1.5 m (azimuth). SAR data (c) 2021 Capella Space all rights reserved.

The difference between the incidence angles, i.e. the intersection angle between the two acquisitions, is about 4° : a small value, which is expected to yield good matching performance; conversely, it may increase the elevation estimation error. The SLC amplitude images were multilooked with a window of 3 by 3, yielding a range resolution of about 2.1 m and an azimuth resolution of about 1.5 m. The multilooked SLC amplitudes of image 1 and 2 are shown in Figure 2 a and b, respectively. We observe that the two images in Figure 2 have slightly different size, which is due to a small difference in the radar sampling frequency of the two acquisitions. This difference is corrected in the resampling stage, where the slave image is resampled to align its size and pixel dimension to the master image's ones.

4. RESULTS

As described in section 2, a region-growing matching technique was applied to the multilooked SAR amplitude images to find associated point pairs. Three iterations of the matching routine were launched, by progressively refining the search area and increasing the minimum point correlation. First, we used a d_{\max} of 10 pixels (≈ 15 m) and a cross-correlation threshold, λ , of 0.1. At the second iteration, d_{\max} was decreased to 5 (≈ 7.5 m) and λ increased to 0.3. At the third iteration d_{\max} and λ were set to 3 (≈ 4.5 m) and 0.5, respectively. The size of the spatial cross-correlation window was set at 32. The elevation pattern point cloud obtained using the adopted technique is shown in Figure 3. We observe that the coverage of the point cloud is not spatially uniform, with densely covered zones interrupted by wide non-covered areas. From a cross-comparison between the point cloud and the terrain properties, most of the gaps seem to concern areas with high slopes and/or dense vegetation. This is justified by the fact that the complicate geometry of high-slope areas and the low coherence of vegetated areas are two factors that typically hinder the performance of the matching algorithm in radargrammetry [3]. The elevation pattern point cloud was spatially interpolated to form the radargrammetric DEM shown in Figure 4. A validation of the obtained result was performed by comparing the radargrammetric DEM with a DEM generated from an airborne lidar sensor, provided by the Spanish National Geographic Institute (IGN). The lidar DEM was generated with a minimum resolution of 0.5 points per m^2 . The lidar DEM of the area of interest is shown in Figure 5. Hence, we computed the pointwise deviation between the elevation pattern point cloud and the lidar DEM, revealing an offset of about +25 m (which was subsequently used for correction), and a standard deviation of 10.2 m. We note that this analysis was realized on the area not affected by the lava flow, as it would bias this validation. The area analysed for validation lies on the right of the black line in Figures 4-5. From a visual analysis, the radargrammetric DEM shows a quite good agreement with the lidar DEM, with a loss of accuracy noticeable in some relief areas.

Figure 3 – Radargrammetry-based elevation pattern point cloud. Colour scale ranging from 250 m (red) to 1970 m (violet).

Figure 4 – Radargrammetric DEM obtained by interpolating the elevation pattern point cloud. Colour scale range: 250 m (red) to 1970 m (blue). The area on the right of the black line was analysed for the validation.

Figure 5 – Lidar-based DEM (from IGN). Colour scale range: 250 m (red) to 1970 m (blue). The area on the right of the black line was analysed for the validation.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper has illustrated some preliminary results investigating the potential of high resolution SLC SAR images collected by Capella Space on-board sensor towards the generation Digital Elevation Model through the radargrammetry approach. Results show a quite good agreement between the generate DEM and a validation lidar DEM in areas not affected by the lava flow coming from the Cumbre Vieja volcanic eruption.

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